

DARE UK

STEADFAST

Education outcomes in young people with diabetes: innovative public involvement and governance to support public trust

REPORT

31st August 2022

STEADFAST: Education outcomes in young people with diabetes: innovative public involvement and governance to support public trust

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1. Project Design and Funding

1.1. The STEADFAST Project: Lay Summary

Type 1 diabetes (referred to as 'diabetes' in this report) is a common long-term health condition affecting 40,000 young people in the UK, requiring daily management. The four UK home nations have legal commitments to support young people with medical conditions in their education. However, there are significant challenges in providing evidence to support interventions. Linking data about diabetes and education could help to provide this evidence base and to provide support for young people with diabetes, their families, health professionals, schools and universities.

Wide public understanding and strong support are critical for the use of sensitive data in research, such as health and education data. Young people are particularly challenging to engage in such conversations. Researchers at Cardiff University (CU), charity Diabetes UK (DUK) and partners previously developed a data access framework and set up a Young People with Diabetes Panel to support research into education outcomes for young people with diabetes.

The STEADFAST project (referred to as 'STEADFAST' from hereon in) has built on this prior work. Through STEADFAST, we explored the best ways to inform, engage and involve young people ages 13-24, their families and the wider public in important issues around the use of their sensitive data for research. We set ourselves a target of participation in the project of at least 50% from under-represented groups, which we defined in this context as young people from the lowest five deciles of deprivation and ethnic minorities. STEADFAST was co-produced by young people living with diabetes. We received 400 expressions of interest from young people to participate, of which 100 young people were consented, and 70 were involved across 19 focus groups. As well as producing this final report, we have developed our findings into a Public Involvement Toolkit for use across other health conditions and social impacts using large-scale linked data. We hope our project will have a broader impact, for example enabling research to support young people with asthma at school or young people with epilepsy in employment.

1.2. Context

STEADFAST is a DARE UK Programme 'Sprint Exemplar' project. The DARE UK Programme aims to design and deliver a co-ordinated and trustworthy national data research infrastructure to support research at scale for public good. The purpose of the Sprint Exemplar projects is to scope out the delivery of a national federated digital research infrastructure to establish the next generation of secure, flexible and interoperable environments for connecting and analysing complex and sensitive multi-disciplinary data at UK scale. The Sprints will contribute to this through exploring driver use cases, technology demonstrators and establishing best practice which reach across UKRI Research Council / Innovate UK domains. We have appreciated and benefitted from the input of the other DARE UK Sprint Exemplar projects throughout.

1.3. Project Team

- **Lead Applicants:** Dr Rob French, Senior Research Fellow, CU and Lucie Burgess, Research Data Hub Programme Director, DUK. **Co-Applicants:** Professor Colin Dyan, Clinical Professor, CU; Dr Julia Townson, Senior Research Fellow, CU; Susie Marques, lay member; Kamini Shah, Head of Research Funding, DUK; Charlotte Austin, Type 1 Lead, DUK; Dr Elizabeth Robertson, Director of Research, DUK; Annette Jack, CEO, Equality Health
- **Public Involvement Co-production Group:** Dr Tom Wylie (Chair), Rebecca Barlow-Noone, Maya Brodie-Dowden, Sophie Jones, Adelina Krusteva, David Stephens, Charlotte Austin. Susie Marques led the public involvement for the application and development stage, but was not involved in the coproduction group during the project.
- **Equality Health: CEO and Co-Founder Annette Jack.** Equality Health is a community engagement agency focused on addressing health inequalities and increasing diverse voices in health research.
- **Helix Data Innovation: Director Lucie Burgess.** Helix Data Innovation is a 'science impact accelerator', helping scientists to accelerate their impact from concept to adoption; HDI led two stakeholder workshops.

- **Additional team members:** PPIE Manager, Karen Rigby, DUK (April-August 2022 100%); Project Manager/Research Associates: Rebecca Milton, CU (~50%); Dr Gwen Moody, CU (March 2022, 20%); Dr Robert Trubey, CU (April–August 2022, 22%); Kim Munnery, CU (February–June 20 %); Ria Sunga, Comms Manager, Equality Health; Amber Turnbull, Social Media Manager, Equality Health; Jona Shehu, Research Associate, Helix Data Innovation.
- **Community Group Support:** Ngozi Omolaiye, Communications and Marketing Manager, Caribbean and African Health Network; Sukhjeen Kaur, CEO / Founder Chronically Brown; Ellouise Simpson, CEO / Founder, Dietician Ellouise; Naomi Awoyemi, CEO / Founder, Research Black; Kirit Mistry, Chair and Keval Sachdev, South Asian Health Action.

1.4. Funding

This work was funded by UK Research & Innovation [Grant Number MC_PC_21031] as part of Phase 1 of the DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) programme, delivered in partnership with Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) and ADR UK (Administrative Data Research UK).

- Funding application submitted: 11th November 2021
- Date the funding was awarded: 8th December 2021
- Funding received: £238,282.60
- Duration: 4th January 2022 to 31st August 2022 (duration 8 months)

1.5. Aims

STEADFAST built on previous pioneering research between CU, DUK and consortium partners, to develop best practice Public Involvement and Information Governance ('IG') frameworks in support of large-scale cross-sector data-driven research for public benefit. Focusing on education outcomes in diabetes as an exemplar, we aimed to improve engagement and involvement of young people living with diabetes. We targeted 50% participation from under-represented groups. We aimed to develop a Public Involvement toolkit which could be applied to other health conditions and linkages beyond health, enabling researchers, data providers, trusted research environments (TREs) and other data stakeholders to learn from our project. We aimed to disseminate our findings and develop recommendations for the UKRI cross-council research infrastructure, enabling our project to have broad impact.

1.6. Planned Outputs

1. Establish a Public Involvement Advisory Group (PIAG) to guide, inform and co-produce the project.
2. To co-produce focus groups with young people living with diabetes and community organisations to ensure our outreach and communications are accessible and meaningful. The focus groups aimed to explore critical issues identified in our previous research:
 - IG framework issues (legal basis for processing; Section 251 approvals; anonymisation; Digital Economy Act).
 - Types of data (e.g. continuous glucose monitoring device data controlled by private companies; sensitive non-health data e.g. employment records); challenging data use (research with a profit-making motive, expectations of how data might be used versus what would not be expected, linkage to non-health data), future use of data (e.g. COPI notices, machine learning, scope for opting-out).
 - Public benefit and trust (legitimate pathways for claiming real-world benefit from research).
3. To develop a Public Involvement toolkit based on our experience, which we will test, develop and evaluate with stakeholders.
4. To facilitate dialogue between young people and our partners.
5. To disseminate the findings of our project to young people with diabetes, researchers and data stakeholders, via the final report, Public Involvement Toolkit and two peer-reviewed research outputs (the latter will be completed by the team after the project end-date as stated in our application)

2. Timeline

The table below gives a summary of the timeline. Regular project team meetings with all partners (DUK, CU, Equality Health, Helix Data Innovation) are not shown.

<p>Month -1: DECEMBER 2021</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funding awarded - Negotiate contract - Centre for Trials Research (CTR) Study adoption group approval sought
<p>Month 1: JANUARY 2022 (Project start date 04/01/2022)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protocol drafted - Sponsorship approval submitted to CU's Research Governance team - Participant information documentation drafted - Microsoft TEAMS space created for cross-organisational working - Risk Assessment / Data protection impact assessments (DPIA) drafted - PPIE Manager post advertised Methods into participant payment explored
<p>Month 2: FEBRUARY 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethics submission to School of Medicine Research Ethics Committee (SMREC) submitted (07/02) - Interviews for PPIE Manager at DUK held - Initial discussions held about systematic review; focus on linked, unconsented data and views of children and young people
<p>Month 3: MARCH 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data Management Plan drafted - Ethical approval granted by SMREC - PIAG Chair appointed
<p>Month 4: APRIL 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PPIE Manager commenced working on STEADFAST - Literature scoping exercise to inform focus groups completed. - Focus group planning commenced - Stakeholder Workshop 1 and 2 planning
<p>Month 5: MAY 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Results from scoping exercise presented to STEADFAST team - Focus group materials developed
<p>Month 6: JUNE 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First focus group held (06/06) - Stakeholder workshop 1 held (09/06)
<p>Month 7: JULY 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final focus group held (05/07) - First draft of Public Involvement Toolkit - Stakeholder workshop 2 held (15/07)
<p>Month 8: AUGUST 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Toolkit completion - Final Report - All invoices generated - All participants and PPIE members remunerated
<p>OCTOBER 2022</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of the Public Involvement Toolkit

3. Governance and Sponsorship

3.1. Governance

Approval was granted by the CU School of Medicine Ethics Committee (SMREC) on 10/03/2022, following initial submission on 07/02/2022. Three further amendments were made to SMREC, all of which were approved. These were as follows:

Amendment 1: Electronic consent added using an online form on DUK website, approved 09/05/2022

Amendment 2: Updated protocol to v3.0 to include: Removed information regarding sponsor as not required, updated details on focus groups, now age specific not subject specific, participants are only expected to attend one focus group which will cover all subjects, details of electronic consent; approved 11/05/2022.

Amendment 3: Updated the protocol to v4.0 to include: Increase in recruitment numbers from 60 to 100. Include an opportunity for interviews as well as focus groups for those who may find focus groups challenging to attend. At the end of the focus groups participants were asked whether they would be interested in being part of a PPIE Group. Updates to existing participant information sheets (PIS) for focus groups: CU will be supporting the focus groups/interviews. Change in number of participants per focus group was adjusted from ten to six to enable more active participation from young people; approved 27 May 2022.

Active Documents: Protocol v4.0, Parental PIS 13-17 Focus Groups v3.0 26.05.22, PIS Focus Groups v3.0 26.05.22, Parental 13-17 Interviews v1.0 26.05.22, PIS Interviews v.10 26.05.22, STEADFAST Assent for Interviews 13-17 years v1.0 26.05.2022, STEADFAST Consent form Parents / Carers Interview v1.0 26.05.22, STEADFAST Consent form Young People Interviews v1.0; approved 26.05.22.

3.2. Sponsorship

The application for sponsorship was submitted to the Research Governance team at CU on 13/01/2022, after consideration it was confirmed that the project did not require a Sponsor, as there was no any recruitment via, or involvement of, NHS organisations.

3.3. Leadership and Management

The project team was accountable to the lead Principal Investigators, Dr Rob French (CU) and Lucie Burgess (DUK). Both lead investigators were governed by the structures and management of their respective organisations. The PIAG, chaired by Dr Tom Wiley, provided invaluable co-production input, steering and advice. The project team met weekly in the first four months of the project and fortnightly thereafter. In reality this was a highly collaborative, non-hierarchical, team approach which greatly benefitted the project. The PIs met regularly with the DARE UK Programme Manager, Michelle Amugi, to discuss progress and challenges.

4. Successes and Challenges

4.1. Successes

Consortium: The already established consortium was highly engaged and collaborative. Individual team members were expert, highly-motivated, committed and enthusiastic. This has provided substantial benefits for the project in terms of generating momentum, driving impact and overcoming challenges. CU, DUK, Equality Health and Helix Data Innovation all worked exceptionally together as a diverse team with multidisciplinary skills and were all proactively involved. Communication across the consortium was efficient and well-coordinated by the CU CTR which contributed to the rapid set-up and delivery. All organisations and team members recognised each others' unique roles and contributions.

Public Involvement Advisory Group: The PIAG made a vital contribution to the project through co-production of messaging, communications, overall direction and advice (see section 6).

Involvement: Equality Health worked with the STEADFAST team to recruit a diverse group of young people to participate in the focus groups. Equality focused on engaging those from ethnic minority and socio-economically disadvantaged groups. Involvement from community groups coordinated by Equality Health (Caribbean and African Health Network; Chronically Brown; Dietician Ellouise; Research Black; South Asian Health Action) was critical to shaping and informing the project overall, and in enabling STEADFAST to meet the diversity and representation

targets. We are grateful to the members of these groups for co-producing messaging, their advice on key issues, and for reaching out to their communities.

Engagement: Equality Health, community organisations and DUK co-produced creative communication materials to recruit young people to the study. This began with a workshop to develop messaging for the recruitment materials that would resonate with the target audience. Community organisations, and members of the PIAG attended. Community organisations then created bespoke communications materials for their network, and used a variety of social media platforms, including Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and TikTok to share these. Materials included digital flyers, twitter cards, short films, and social media posts with graphics. Some organisations also directly messaged ‘influencers’ interested in health issues like diabetes to share information. DUK highlighted STEADFAST on its Facebook page, Instagram account and via online ‘Research Fridays’.

Use of creative media channels and platforms: One of the outputs was a short film (see <https://youtu.be/baJgBYPRxxY>, 2 minutes long) produced by Equality, Duke Al Durham, a spoken word artist with diabetes and a DUK Supporter, and FreshRB, a creative video production community interest company. The film captured Duke rapping about his experience of living with diabetes, and sharing information about STEADFAST. This film was used to encourage young people (males in particular) to participate in STEADFAST, and was well-received by all stakeholders. Overall, recruitment for STEADFAST highlighted the need for creative communications to engage young people from ethnic minority and socially disadvantaged groups, including: Co-produced communications, tailored to specific group: Film and the spoken word: Social media platforms targeted at a younger population; Working with social media influencers.

Participation from Young People: The interest in the project was overwhelming, over 400 expressions of interest received from young people ages 13-24. Our target was to consent a maximum of 60 participants and to run six focus groups. This was increased to a maximum of 100 participants due to available time and resources. 70 young people attended a total of 19 focus groups over a one month period. The focus groups were made substantially smaller (maximum six participants) and were run as single sessions of two hours, rather than three sessions of one hour, to minimise drop-out. Young people were compensated for their time with a £50 Love2Shop, Amazon voucher or BACS payment. These options were offered to encourage inclusive participation from all backgrounds.

Diversity and Representation: Due to the extensive outreach of the involvement and engagement efforts by the STEADFAST team, representation in terms of ethnicity and deprivation equivalent to the national diversity of the National Diabetes Audit (NDA) and National Paediatric Diabetes Audit (NPDA) was achieved. Equality Health co-produced a video by Duke Al Durham and Fresh RB Productions to appeal specifically to young men (section 5). Young people with diabetes through social media platforms and the focus groups were involved. We provided advice to young people with diabetes on managing diabetes at school and received excellent feedback from focus group participants.

Collaboration and Commitment: The team effort from the collaborators, participants, community members, PPIE group and project team was exceptional. Every member of the team worked above and beyond their resourcing to ensure that this was a success and this resulted in the aims of STEADFAST being achieved.

4.2. Challenges

Project Design: STEADFAST was designed as a research project, beyond a Public Involvement activity (which would not in itself require ethical approval) in order to be able to produce peer-reviewed research outputs. The design of STEADFAST as a research project as well as a public involvement activity created challenges; our project was heavily focused on engagement with young people, requiring best-practice research governance and safeguarding, all of which took time and effort. The response from young people was overwhelming; we received over 400 expressions of interest to take part, and we wanted to include as many participants as possible. This required substantial administration and multiple amendments to SMREC. Ethical amendments are not a rapid process, yet the project was running to exceptionally tight deadlines which presented potential delays.

Staff Recruitment: Due to the rapid nature of the Sprint Exemplar projects, there was insufficient time from project funding approval to the start date to establish a complete project team. To overcome this, within the CTR at CU the role was split over a number of individuals. This also created opportunities as we benefited from diverse skills across the team. Within DUK, the post for PPIE Manager was advertised in early January 2022, but the

recruitment process meant that the PPIE manager was unable to start work on the project until April 2022, four months into the project. We were able to recruit an excellent PPIE Manager for the post on secondment from Royal Devon University Healthcare NHS Foundation Trust.

Public Involvement Advisory Group: The originally identified PPIE Chair was unable to fulfil the role once the project had been funded, which resulted in a new PPIE Chair needing to be appointed, three months after the project started. Recruitment to the PIAG was limited by the late appointment of a PPIE Manager. Earlier recruitment may have benefited the PIAG in terms of the diversity of representation.

Engagement and participant recruitment: A key challenge was how to reach young people on traditionally used social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter, as posts initially reflected low levels of engagement. Over the eight weeks, the team met to consider ideas to increase engagement and participation. Solutions included:

- Creating short films for social media platforms that drew more attention than text
- Sharing short films on TikTok, where more young people interacted
- Stating that participants would be compensated for taking part
- Directly messaging influencers with diabetes, groups, and young people on social media

Project timeframe: A longer timeframe, would have meant the community organisations and DUK's comms team could have worked together more effectively on the programme, to jointly brand and share community organisations' materials.

Resourcing: STEADFAST was delivered in eight months, from set-up to completion, thanks to the considerable commitment of team members who excelled in their roles and went 'above and beyond' to deliver the project against a challenging time frame. A longer timeframe and extra allocation of resources are recommended for similar projects.

5. Outputs

5.1. Project Plan: Aims and Associated Outputs

Aims	Outputs
<p>1. Work with young people, their families and our partners to develop robust, meaningful and enriched PPIE and IG models which foster public confidence and trust in research requiring large-scale, sensitive, unconsented data linkage.</p>	<p>400 expressions of interest were received, 100 individuals consented (13-24 years old), 19 focus groups were held over a one month, 70 individuals participated, ~50 hours of focus group data collected. These data were qualitatively analysed by CTR and DUK and the results will be published in a peer reviewed journal. These data contributed to the Public Involvement toolkit development. Young people provided excellent feedback on their experiences of taking part in the project.</p>
<p>2. Involve and engage under-represented communities to develop this framework; particularly young people, those from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds and BAME communities; targeting 50% involvement from under-represented groups.</p>	<p>Equal representation between age groups 13-14, 15-17, 18-24. Of 100 consented, 38 males, 1 non-binary, 61 female. 29% were in deciles 1-5 of deprivation across England and Wales by LSOA 20% from ethnic minorities (representative), due to challenges with linkage we were not able to create this breakdown for participants located in Scotland and Northern Ireland. In terms of conversion from consent to attending focus groups, there are no differences by age, gender or Index of Multiple Deprivation. A difference by ethnicity; generally was present, conversion rates were higher for all ethnic minority groups than for white (white conversion rate=68%) except Black / African / Caribbean / Black British.</p>
<p>3. Test the potential of the novel, successful and acceptable IG approach previously developed for diabetes-education research to be extended to other conditions and social impacts e.g. employment, investigating the opportunities and challenges of this approach.</p>	<p>The Public Involvement toolkit, designed in consultation with young people and stakeholders can be used across other health conditions and social impacts to inform the DARE UK program. In particular, the Public Involvement Toolkit is aimed at researchers and funders or anyone looking to involve young people aged 13 to 24 in research involving large-scale or unconsented data. 28 stakeholders contributed to two stakeholder workshops and provided multiple real-world examples of where the Public Involvement toolkit could be used in their research.</p>
<p>4. Develop a Public Involvement toolkit for PPIE and IG based on Aims 1-3 which can be more broadly applied to research investigating the relationship between health/biomedicine with characteristics beyond health e.g. employment, justice, social services.</p>	<p>A Public Involvement Toolkit has been developed, based on input from young people during the focus groups, the two stakeholder workshops held with 28 stakeholders, and the experiences of the project team.</p>
<p>5. Disseminate and evaluate our findings and develop recommendations for the UKRI cross-council research infrastructure, enabling our project to have impact.</p>	<p>Young people gave important feedback on their views around use of data for research and for the collection of audit data for the NDA/NPDA which we have disseminated to these stakeholders. Recommendations for public involvement in research involving young people are provided in the Toolkit. The Toolkit will be disseminated through the website and social media channels of DUK, CU, Equality Health, community groups, DARE UK.</p>

5.2. Other Notable Outputs

Outputs	Status
Project set-up	Completed
Ethical Approval	Completed
Recruited PPIE Manager	Completed
PIAG established	Completed
Engagement with community groups	Completed
Rapid reviews	Completed: a scoping exercise for the focus groups from the existing literature. Details will be used in the two peer-reviewed publications which are in progress.
Recruitment to focus groups	Completed: 400 expressions of interest, 100 consented, 70 participants attended 19 focus groups.
Hold two stakeholder workshops	Completed: 28 delegates across both.
Target of 50% involvement from under-represented groups	Results: 19% of focus group participants were from ethnic minorities. 28% of focus group participants were from the lowest five deciles of deprivation. Although we did not achieve our 50% target, young people are themselves challenging to involve in research.
Toolkit development	Ongoing: A copy to be completed by 31/08/2022. Completed final design to be completed by mid-September 2022.
Involvement materials to be developed	Completed. Spoken word piece by poet Duke Al Durham to encourage young men to participate: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=baJgBYPRxxY
Dissemination	Ongoing: Planned launch October 2022
Evaluation	Completed: Internal team evaluation via final team meeting, reflected in the final report.
Final Report	Completed: Submitted to funder on 31/08/2022
Research manuscripts (2)	In development: This was not a commitment from the original proposal and will be submitted for publication by 31/12/2022.

6. Public Involvement Advisory Group (PIAG)

6.1. Overview

The PIAG members were recruited from the existing DUK Young People’s Panel. Meetings began in April 2022 with a short summary of the project, the lay summary and draft terms of reference. Discussion of Chair’s responsibilities was held and the Chair and one other member expressed interest in attending all STEADFAST team meetings but without obligation. The PIAG were consulted on all aspects, especially in terms of reaching out to and working with participants with diabetes. Strategies and approaches were adapted following and according to advice from the PIAG. The PIAG was involved in the co-production of participant facing materials. Conversations with PIAG members helped facilitators to feel confident that they could create an environment to discuss data and have a soundboard for how to best engage people living with diabetes about data sharing.

6.2. How the PIAG Input Optimised Our Approach

Participant Recruitment:

- Discussions of appropriate language e.g. ‘online chat’ or ‘online group discussion’ rather than ‘focus group’ when communicating with young people
- Incorporate ‘chance to meet other people with diabetes’ in project promotion, as some PIAG members had not previously had this opportunity
- PIAG members shared social media posts to broaden the project’s reach
- Suggested use of established networks, events and influencers to encourage recruitment

- Particular emphasis was put on the need to focus on these routes in communities which haven't been heard from enough, and to look for innovative ways of doing this

Focus Group Content Development:

- Chair involvement at every development meeting and team meeting
- Critical not to assume participant knowledge of data collection and data processing and the importance of both establishing this within the conversation and framing subsequent discussions based on what the facilitators were told was emphasised given the sensitive nature of consent
- Identified four out of the seven presented themes from the scoping exercise that would be most crucial to cover in focus groups
- Supported the use of scenarios to bring the issues to be discussed to life, and how to present these issues:
 - Who is looking? (private vs research vs personal)
 - Why are they looking? (benefit, use and evidence of benefit)
 - What are they looking at? (types of data, levels of data and personal 'my life' data versus statistics, anonymised / identifiable)
 - Privacy vs trust and the importance of respecting participants' views, incorporating clear communication and proper consent
 - Flexibility of communication was emphasised (which should be made clear before participation): giving people the option to keep video off or exclusively use the chat function.
 - Offering the opportunity to let participants talk to each other afterwards or in breaks was supported
 - A growing Slido poll was suggested rather than a different word cloud for each session to build an overall picture, the PIAG helped design new questions to ask on Slido after arising themes from initial focus groups
 - Using short bursts of video to communicate has been normalised for young people and could be looked into doing this more in the future

Analysis of Qualitative Data:

- New themes and interpretation
- Other demographics which could impact experience e.g. age of diagnosis, diagnosis in paediatric services or adult services, input from grandparents, parents with engaging jobs, parental help, level of understanding from care providers: parents / teachers / school nurses / grandparents / siblings
- Many of the themes identified are about issues surrounding support provided by people with knowledge or a lack of knowledge
- The PIAG expressed a wish to write a commentary piece to support the qualitative paper when it is published which is supported by some journals

Key advice for STEADFAST Toolkit:

- Taking part in PPIE should feel like a conversation that delivers insight which steers the research in a way which is acted upon and then made evident to members
- People with diabetes are a unique group containing very different personal experiences, views and access to technology, that you wouldn't be able to take account of in research without good PPIE, as for any health condition
- Getting people's voices into research requires a range of perspectives from a range of backgrounds to ensure decision-making incorporates multiple perspectives. Varied recruitment processes must reflect this
- Being involved in PPIE is fun and as a patient you get to see how new treatments, guidelines and knowledge come about

7. Findings

7.1. Scoping Review Findings

The four themes below were selected for a scoping exercise of existing literature. The findings from the scoping review informed the development of the focus group content. The full results of the scoping review can be made available to interested individuals on request.

Summary of Findings 'Unconsented Data':

- Minimal research has been conducted on the thoughts and understanding of young people with regards to unconsented data. A study with a similar design to STEADFAST has been conducted on childhood vision research.
- Literature found that young people felt that even if data is anonymous, opt-in consent is still important because of etiquette and data 'ownership'.
- Overall it seems that if for public benefit, then data could be used without consent, yet if consent opportunities were available they should be sought.

Summary of Findings 'Types of Data':

- No results on what data young people think are currently collected about them, a lot around online privacy.
- Results from a focus group provides types of data and the participants categorise where they'd be happy to have these data shared, so can conclude the type of data is considered to be sensitive.
- Two videos created within CTR explain what routine data is and how researchers use these data: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OTSXVSqIF9E> and https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f5JUjT_oh48 these would be useful resources.
- Overall if data linkage is for public benefit it seems to be widely accepted.
- Generally understanding of data linkage is poor among adults, but once explained and the benefits understood it is well received and supported.

Summary of Findings 'Trust and Trustworthiness':

- Most evidence is from research focused on adults. Three studies looked at views of older adolescents.
- Overall message from previous research is that trust in data linkage is "highly conditional and variable".
- Trust (adults) dependent upon: perceived value of research; de-identification; data security; no profit.
- Trust (adults) is higher for NHS / academic / charity sector, but much lower for commercial / private. Adolescents were similarly sceptical about sharing with corporations, but also concerned about sharing identifiable data with schools and researchers.
- Broad support for the use of health data for linkage, less evidence for support for linking to education data, or other non-health data.
- People are less comfortable consenting to ongoing future linkage vs short term linkage.
- Trust generally improves when more information is provided about what will happen with their data, or if commercial organisations are clearly using for public health benefit.
- Trust dependent on perceived benefits / use – has to have some obvious public health benefits
- Trust varies by demographic subgroups, lower income and minority groups generally show less trust in organisations linking their data.

Summary of Findings 'Anonymised Data':

- Among adults, little understanding of what 'anonymised' data means / ability to distinguish between different levels of anonymisation, de-identification, etc.
- Findings show that as long as people feel that the data is anonymised, they don't think consent is needed.
- Young people in one study felt that even if data is anonymous, opt-in consent is still important because of etiquette and data 'ownership'.
- Findings show people are happier to share data at group / cohort level but concerned about disclosure risks at individual level (and schools having access to health data, etc).

7.2. Demographics of Focus Group Participants

Breakdown by Age:

Breakdown by Gender: Because of the age range and the varied ages that young people in different regions transfer into adult diabetes services, data from young people will be recorded either in the National Diabetes Audit (NDA) or National Paediatric Diabetes Audit (NPDA).

NDA 2019-2020	NPDA* 2020	FOCUS GROUP ATTENDEES	CONSENTED
Male 56.9%	Male 52.7%	Male 27	Male 40
Female 43.1%	Female 47.3%	Female 42	Female 63
		Non-Binary 1	Non-Binary 1

Breakdown by Ethnicity: 81% white, 19% other ethnic backgrounds, shown in more detail below.

ETHNICITY	TOTAL CONSENTED	TOTAL AT FOCUS GROUPS	TOTAL AT FOCUS GROUPS %	NDA 2019-2020	NPDA 2021
Asian or Asian Background	5	4	6.0%	3.5%	6.7%
Any other Asian Background	1	1			
Bangladeshi	1	1			
Indian	2	2			
Pakistani	1	0			
Black, Black British, Caribbean or African Background	6	4	6.0%	2.3%	4.0%
African	5	4			
Any other Black, Black British or Caribbean	1	0			
Mixed or Multiple Ethnic Groups	5	3	4.0%	1.1%	3.0%
Any other Mixed or multiple ethnic	3	2			
White and black African	1	0			
White and Black Caribbean	1	1			
Other Ethnic Group	1	1	0.1%	1.1%	2.3%
Any other Ethnic Group	1	1			
White	87	57	81.0%	82.6%	79.3%
Any other white background	4	4			
English, Welsh, Scottish, Northern Irish or British	82	52			
Unknown	1	1	0.1%	9.5%	4.7%
TOTAL	104	70			

7.3. Focus Group Findings

Our key findings are being written up into a qualitative research paper for a publication in a peer-reviewed journal. High level results are presented below.

Support for Diabetes Management in Education and Work:

- There was a variety of support available for young people at school. Examples of best practice were often associated with a greater number of young people with diabetes at a school and teachers being more experienced as a result. Young people often experienced a dramatic decline in support when transitioning from primary to secondary school. University students received better support with clear procedures to access that support. In almost every group there were examples of experience of very poor provision and difficulties negotiating appropriate support.
- Diabetes requires an exceptional degree of maturity and autonomy to treat and manage day-to-day blood glucose levels. Further, the treatment of diabetes varies considerably from person to person, which makes it particularly challenging for teachers and support staff, who, as a result, are often required to rely on the child's

own expertise of the condition. young people need to have a degree of flexibility to access glucose, snacks and drinks for hypoglycemia treatment; visit the bathroom; use mobile phones and other technologies (CGM, insulin pumps), in a way that is often restricted in a usual classroom environment.

- Conflicts in negotiating this flexibility between teachers, support staff and students, as well the stress of managing diabetes, were raised and discussed by young people.
- Issues raised covered: lack of appropriate exam provisions (including not being able to have a phone in the exam hall so not being able to check blood sugar levels), not being allowed to eat when blood glucose levels were low, drink or go to the toilet if blood glucose levels were high, inject in a public area or carry insulin with them; not being able to go on class trips due to lack of support; being penalised with detentions due to absence rates. Young people especially those who had experienced primary school or the early years of secondary school often struggled to communicate their needs to teachers who did not respect their opinion because they were so young.
- When teachers engaged with the young people about their condition, young people felt more supported and safe in the knowledge that their condition was being taken seriously.

Attitudes to Use of Linked Data for Research:

- Very few participants were aware their identifiable data were used for the NDA/NPDA. While most young people were willing for their data to be shared to support this purpose, many would like to see more effort made to inform them about this. There was a strong message that posters in GP surgeries do not go far enough.

Attitudes to Sharing Health Data:

- Young people were generally not willing to share their identifiable health data with future employers, social media companies, teachers, advertising companies or online contacts. However, they were generally willing to share them (>80%) with DUK, makers of Flash / CGM devices, parents or guardians, researchers, GPs / doctors and other NHS healthcare professionals.
- Attitudes did not vary significantly by age, although the younger age group was even less likely to feel comfortable sharing identifiable health data with teachers compared to the other age groups. Further, the older age group was even less likely than most to share identifiable health data with future employers.
- Lack of knowledge about use of data for research without consent.
- Mistrust of sharing data about mental health or counselling visits.

Attitudes to Sharing Education Data:

- Most young people were happy to share identifiable education data with DUK, future employers, parents or guardians, teachers, GPs / doctors and NHS healthcare professionals (>80%). However, they were not happy to share them with social media, advertising companies or their online contacts.
- Young people did not want to be defined by their numbers such as blood glucose levels; they wanted context to be provided about their personal situation, while respecting their privacy.

Attitudes to Using Data Without Consent:

- Many of the young people we spoke to were positive about the use of data without consent. But they wanted greater knowledge and awareness that it was being used without consent. There were a few people who felt that consent should always be sought; and others that felt it was conditional on who wanted to access that data.

Attitudes to Sharing Anonymised Data:

- Anonymisation of data was generally viewed positively. Removing identifiable details made young people more likely to share data with people and organisations that were less trusted.

9. Impact

9.1. Overview

STEADFAST's main aim was to develop and experiment with methods to involve young research using linked, unconsented data at scale, using education outcomes for young people with diabetes as a real-world use-case. Our project was designed to inform DARE UK Programme requirements for the design of cross-council digital research environments and with anticipated broader impact across health/biomedical and social science research. In addition to the dissemination of this final report, the Public Involvement Toolkit be widely disseminated by DARE UK, DUK and all project partners, enabling the wider research community to learn from our experience. The STEADFAST findings will be shared with stakeholders including NHIR, National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement and its Scottish equivalent, the Diabetes Research Steering Groups (DUK) and other networks (including those of the participants of the STEADFAST workshops, e.g., Generation R).

9.2. Evaluation against Impact Objectives

In our proposal we stated a number of impact objectives, which are reproduced below along with our self-evaluation of the impact we achieved during the project, and the further steps that need to be taken by project partners and the DARE UK programme to enable long-term delivery of impact.

Impact objective	Self-evaluation
Building the trust of young people living with diabetes to support large-scale research into education outcomes with diabetes	Feedback from young people is provided below. 83% of participants said that they had 'a lot better' understanding of unconsented data and its uses in research after the focus groups. Young people in general were not aware of uses of their data for audit or research. Our findings are not representative of all 40,000 children and young people with diabetes in the UK and substantially more outreach and engagement would be needed to promulgate this understanding across all young people living with diabetes.
Inform, investigate and communicate the perspectives of young people and their families around the benefits and risks of using their sensitive data for research across health and education	Feedback from young people is provided below. 66% of participants who gave feedback strongly agreed that they felt 'informed' following the sessions. Opinions about data sharing and about diabetes and education are summarised above and will be submitted for publication in two qualitative papers in peer-reviewed journals by summer 2022. We found that there was a paucity of academic literature in both areas. Individual advice was given to young people and their parents/guardians during the project to support them in dealing with issues raised about support for diabetes management at school and college.
Develop our findings into a toolkit for use by stakeholders researching health conditions in young people and wider social impacts such as education, employment and public policy so that they can benefit from our approach.	The Public Involvement Toolkit was a key output of STEADFAST and is currently being finalised. It will be disseminated by the project partners and DARE UK in October 2022.
Involve groups often under-represented in research, including young people, particularly from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds and ethnic minority communities; community groups and the wider public. Through outreach to under-represented groups, break down barriers to representation and diversity, reducing bias and leading to improved research outcomes.	Diversity and representation in focus group participants was equivalent to nationally-representative statistics in the NDA and NPDA. Without the substantial outreach and engagement delivered in this project, this would not have been achieved. However, despite our considerable efforts, we would have liked representation from ethnic minorities and from the lowest deciles of deprivation to be higher. Our impact demonstrates the expertise, efforts and budgets to deliver successful representative public involvement in research.
Provide a real-world use-case to support broader research requiring large-scale linkage of health/biomedical and social	Stakeholders attending the two stakeholder workshops in June and July 2022 provided tangible examples of wider potential impact. However our focus in this project was narrow and we acknowledge that what worked for STEADFAST may not generalise; while our methods were

<p>science/administrative data (e.g. education, employment, justice, social services).</p>	<p>generalisable to involvement of young people, every research project will need to take account of its own communities and context. One of the Stakeholders, the Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health (RCPCH), has identified the challenge of the opt-out for individuals contributing data to national audits. We are working with the RCPCH to collate young people's views on mechanisms for opting out and whether young people would support setting aside the common law duty of confidentiality for the purposes of the audits.</p>
<p>Inform DARE UK programme requirements for next-generation trusted research environments across UKRI sectors. Generate impact for the DARE UK programme stakeholders, including researchers linking data across health/biomedical sciences and administrative/social science, data custodians, the NHS, government, charities and policy-makers.</p>	<p>The delivery of longer-term impact within DARE UK will require further focus and resources to integrate our findings into the DARE UK programme. The Public Involvement Toolkit is aimed at researchers using large-scale unconsented data at scale and we feel that we have generated tangible impact for this stakeholder group. However this will also require continuing dissemination from project partners after the project end-date.</p>
<p>This will impact treatment, care, public policy and services. Ultimately it will improve young people's long-term health, educational potential, socio-economic outcomes, enhance quality of life and reduce NHS costs.</p>	<p>Longer-term impact will be generated from the two qualitative research papers (to be submitted to peer-reviewed journals by Summer 2023) and continuing research led by Cardiff University into education and health outcomes for young people with diabetes, for which future funding is being sought. These efforts will be supported by communications from partners.</p>

9.2. Participant Impact

The following comments made by participants during the focus groups illustrate the impact of STEADFAST:

Learning: *'I liked it and because because I could learn' (13, male). 'I've learned a lot' (22, male).*

Helping Others: *'Yeah. For me, it's about helping improve the healthcare and research for future people' (21, female). 'To help with the research, I felt like I had a perspective that would be useful to it.And and yeah, the money was a nice push as well' (18, female).*

Engaging with Others About Shared Experiences: *'I think it's really helpful and it's good to hear other people's experiences...it makes you feel less alone' (22, female). 'We've never really got the opportunity to, like, talk about it with other people who do, like, understand and go through the same thing' (21, female). 'It was nice to hear, like, opinions that other people have like because sometimes you feel like you're just like, uh, I'm on this boat alone kind of thing' (22, female). 'I think it's been interesting to hear other people's experiences around the same thing because I've I've known I've had a few friends over the years who have been diabetic, but I've never really spoken to other diabetics about this kind of stuff. So I would definitely want to do something again' (20, female). 'It's good to just be able to talk about this kind of thing sometimes. Just talk to some other like minded people to just or not minded in this case or other people with diabetes just to kind of share your experience and see how other people deal with certain things can really help' (14, male).*

Evidence of Research Benefits: *'For me it was mainly being able to voice my opinions and obviously help' (21, female). 'Yeah, I just enjoy learning about stuff that's going on to make it like to improve diabetes, especially diabetes and education, because that's something I feel quite strongly about having...being in high school like for the last six years and it's just like there's not been much of a change like since first year. I'm still having these same chats with these same teachers and they're still not getting it' (17, female). 'I think that this session has been very insightful' (22, male).*

9.3. Participant Feedback

We obtained feedback from 53/70 (76%) participants.

*already know a lot about the subject

Participants were also asked what they would change about the session and while most would not change anything, some provided some recommendations:

- *'I would like one to one as I felt a bit nervous talking in front of people'*
- *'making it more about finding it a bit more in-depth of people's stories and being reassured that something positive may come out of this'*
- *'seeing a wider range of people would've made the session more interesting'*
- *'Perhaps more frequent and shorter breaks, and it would be better if people had their cameras on because it makes it easier to talk openly'*

10. Conclusion

Overall, the STEADFAST project achieved its aims and objectives and delivered tangible impact. We found that good public involvement has the potential to foster the conditions for public trust in large-scale data analytics. The findings from STEADFAST will support future research and researchers working with large-scale data from young people.

STEADFAST contributed to the DARE UK Programme aim of designing and delivering innovative UK-wide data research infrastructure that is coordinated, demonstrates trustworthiness and supports research at scale for public good. Young people were generally supportive of large-scale data analytics, as long as it was for public good and not private profit. *'if someone asks something about [diabetes] I'm 9 times out of 10 gonna answer it. ..., because it's going to be used for a good cause. What it's going to be used for is something that's going to benefit me and others as well so I wouldn't have a problem with that'* (14 year old male). However, young people wanted greater transparency when their data were being used without consent, supporting the concept of more participatory data governance models. They also wanted more tangible demonstrations of outcomes and benefits from this type of research.

STEADFAST's Public Involvement Toolkit will enable UK researchers to use appropriate techniques and skills to involve the public and to harness the full power of linked datasets. Ideas from young people as to how they could best be informed about the use of their sensitive data has the potential to lead to changes in methods for research and public involvement. However, organisations such as HDRUK, DUK and NHS Digital have considerably more engagement and outreach work to do with young people to explain the rationale for data sharing without consent, the methods used and benefits if this potential is to be realised.

A key finding of our project was that public involvement and co-production of research requires time, creativity, sufficient funding and specific public involvement expertise. Public involvement should be properly budgeted for and funded, and appropriate skills nurtured.

We would especially like to thank all the young people and their families who were involved in STEADFAST, who generously contributed their time and shared their views; the members of our Public Involvement Advisory Group and the community organisations who supported our work.

Lucie Burgess, Dr Rob French and The STEADFAST team
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